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ECOLOGICAL REMOTE FIRE MONITORING BASED ON THE FIRMS INFORMATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: Technological advances have affected all aspects of Earth observation data, including improvements in characteristics and capabilities for near-real-time global data processing and monitoring. The synergies of remote sensing, geographic information systems (GIS), the Internet and mobile technologies are revolutionizing the way satellite information is archived and disseminated. The Fire Information System for Resource Management (FIRMS), funded by NASA, is just one of many examples illustrating the increasing ease with which Earth observation data becomes available to a wide range of users. In the article, we describe how satellite remote sensing and GIS technologies have been integrated to provide MODIS data on active fires. It can be used by the Ministry of Emergencies, energy companies and other organizations to assess the potential impact of the fire on infrastructure and assets.

Keywords: FIRMS, fire monitoring sistem, forest fire, human safety, satellite observation, NASA

Every year, millions of hectares of forest burn in Russia, flora and fauna die, sometimes fire approaches settlements, threatening people's lives, millions of city residents choke on smog fires. According to estimates as of August 2021, currently the area of fires in the forests of Russia has exceeded 8 million hectares. Along with the loss of life, the financial consequences of these fires are enormous. Fires cause huge losses, damage or destroy houses, enterprises, cars and other types of property [1].

However, while fires burn, they cannot hide from satellites. Even in the most remote corners of the globe, their thermal signatures can be detected by sensors aboard Earth observation satellites. The ability to quickly provide

information on the approximate location and movement of individual forest fires with instruments on board Earth observation satellites is a global success story that helps save lives and property.

Providing information on the hot spots found by devices onboard Earth observation satellites in the mode close to real time, is the opportunity available more than ten years by means of a control system resources FIRMS., developed in the University of Maryland and supported by the National agency of the USA on aeronautics and a research of space (further – NASA).

Space monitoring is the most important source of information that allows you to quickly respond to the occurrence of man-made and natural emergencies (hereinafter – emergency situations), objectively assess their scale and degree of damage, effectively combat the consequences of accidents and disasters, and increase the reliability of the forecast of crisis situations. For Russia, characterized by huge territories and special climatic conditions, the application of the results of analysis of remote sensing data is especially relevant.

This type of monitoring makes it possible to detect major accidents, disasters and emergencies, in particular, emergency spills of oil products, subsidence and failure of soil as a result of mining, pollution during mining and transportation of minerals, monitor their dynamics, provide information support for the decision-making process, as well as assess the environmental situation and identify sources of pollution [2].

The first request for active fire data from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (hereinafter – MODIS) came from the US Forest Service immediately after the launch of MODIS to help extinguish forest fires on the border of Idaho and Montana. This has led to the rapid development of a rapid response system. Initially, the system was available only for North America, but since then its coverage has expanded significantly.

FIRMS provide active fire data (including the approximate location of the detected access point) using NASA medium resolution MODIS spectroradiometers and a set of visible infrared imaging radiometers (VIIRS), typically within an hour of satellite observation, with imagery available within four to five hours.

FIRMS detects fires from satellite images. Information about fires is a product of automated thematic qualification of ground remote sensing data, namely, on the basis of automatic recording of high reflection in thermal channels of the solar radiation spectrum in space images from the MODIS camera installed on Terra, Aqua satellites. The period and time of renewal depends on the flight of the satellite of a given territory, in the average period is 2-4 times a day. The orbits of satellites are constructed in such a way that each of them turns out to be the same territory once a day, once in the day and once at night. The periodicity of the monitoring area depends on the reflectors and geographical location by latitude [3].

FIRMS combines remote sensing and GIS technologies to provide fire data worldwide. The information is delivered in a mode close to real (about an hour after the passage of the satellite), with a relatively small file size and easily accessible format.

The NASA Earth Satellite Monitoring (Earth Observation System) program allows the free use of space survey data from Terra and Aqua devices and direct reception of these data. Received data is fed into automatic chain of processing and preparation of products, which includes stage of primary processing of data, creation on the basis of basic products of space survey, preparation of products for Internet access and publication in the form of service. On the fire map, information from these satellites is used to detect probable fire centers and to prepare daily observation coverage with space images [4].

Fire detection algorithms in automatic mode are based on strong radiation in the infrared range (context-threshold algorithm). The difference in pixel temperature brightness reflects the difference between the temperature of the fires and the earth's surface, and information from other spectral channels helps mask clouds. In addition, thresholds filter thermal anomalies that are unlikely to apply to fires. Thus, the output of the algorithm is a mask of pixels classified as "hotspots" of fires and their brightness characteristics.

According to the US Forest Service, dry wood fuel ignites when it reaches a temperature of about 540 ° F (provided there is enough oxygen), and wildfire burns at temperatures that can exceed 1500 ° F. This heat serves as a beacon for orbital sensors such as MODIS and VIIRS, which detect the emitted energy.

Fire monitoring data is a contextual assessment, the degree of accuracy of which is influenced by many factors. Fires are very likely to be detected in cloudless or cloudless weather. In addition, the probability of fire detection is affected by factors such as difference temperature and fire size. Archival layers of space images can be used to assess the state of clouds at the time of fire observations.

MODIS orbits the Earth aboard the Terra and Aqua satellites, while VIIRS is aboard the NASA/NOAA Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership (hereinafter Suomi NPP) joint satellite. If a wildfire is burning and MODIS or VIIRS flies over it in its normal operating mode, the energy emitted by the fire will be detected.

Figure 1 – Each orange point in this image of the map of Russia since July 30, 2021 is a thermal point detected in the last 24 hours using a moderate resolution image spectroradiometer (MODIS) on board the Earth observation satellites Terra and AquaNASA [5]

When MODIS detects a thermal anomaly that may indicate a wildfire or any significant heat source, the computer algorithm determines the center of the 1 km² region in which the anomaly is detected. This location is mapped and available to fire crews and forest managers (and anyone with access to the FIRES Fire Map) within an hour of observation provides an approximate location of a potential wildfire or burning point [6].

This data is an invaluable resource for managing ongoing fires and tracking their spread. In accordance with NASA's open data policy, all MODIS and VIIRS data and products are fully in the public domain. This policy also applies to algorithms used for data processing, as well as to application program interfaces (APIs) that facilitate the use of data. This means that anyone anywhere in the world who has access to a computer with an Internet connection can access the FIRMS, MODIS and VIIRS data.

The combination of FIRMS, together with thermal anomaly data loaded directly from MODIS and VIIRS during satellite observation (a process called "direct reading"), can provide regional and national firefighters with a complete understanding of the location, extent and intensity of current forest fire activity across much of Russia.

Clusters are a group of individual thermal fires. Grouping is based on an automatic algorithm and does not guarantee 100% accuracy. Clustering helps:

- visualize a large number of thermocouples and improve the readability of information on an overview scale
 - monitor fire dynamics;
 - Estimate the fire strength – the area where more thermal flares are clustered is a sign of a more powerful fire;

- approximately estimate the area of the active fire by the total contour of the thermocouples included in the cluster;
- approximately estimate total area of burned-out area for the selected observation period;
- on a small map scale (levels 1-3), fire clusters are rendered as a dynamic "heat map," which allows you to quickly view and analyze a large amount of data [7].

Fire clusters also help visually filter out "false fires," which appear, for example, due to glare, and short-term fires, which are caused, for example, by dry grass and do not yet pose a real threat. Two groups of thermal flares, which a few days ago were one fire, and then split, will still be part of the same cluster for the entire total combustion period, even if for part of the period they are displayed in different contours. Intuitively, clusters can be considered correlated with burnt out territories.

A significant part of the fires identified by satellite data can relate to the so-called man-made heat sources. These are primarily industrial facilities, for example, factory pipes or flares for burning associated gas. In order not to cause confusion in the perception of information about fires, the service uses a special algorithm for additional filtering of man-made sources.

Since man-made objects are characterized by a cluster of thermowells in one local area and have high recurrence of combustion, on the basis of constant detection of such areas, we compile a database of man-made objects, which is additionally supplemented with information from open sources on the location of large industrial enterprises and deposits. If the identified fire source falls into such an area of a man-made source, then it is given the appropriate status. Clusters and points of anthropogenic anomalies have a special symbol on the map.

Automatic fire detection data are probabilistic and selective. Therefore, to obtain a more accurate and complete result, it is necessary to use verification tools based on additional sources of information: information from users, images from video cameras, automatic or manual processing of data from high-resolution satellites, etc.

Remote sensing data are used in many areas of our country and around the world. Since this industry is not old and is developing quite recently, at the modern technological level, and accordingly, the gradual introduction of the results of space activities in all areas of our life and national economy is underway. The network of mobile stations receives remote sensing data from various satellites, thereby achieving the results that after the survey, about 30 minutes later, we receive ground sensing data, developed and ready for further transfer for further use.

Figure 2 – Program Fire Monitoring Complex

FIRMS will be interested in logging companies, power units of various countries of the world, oil and agricultural companies, environmental organizations, municipal departments. It allows you to obtain a large list of products for information support of the fire situation: databases of all identified thermal and man-made heat sources (plants, flares of associated gas combustion, fields) with geographical reference to the area, clusters (circuits) of fires, detailed and overview space images, regional statistics, fire notifications, API interface [8].

The complex consists of the following modules:

1. Automatic fire detection.
2. Monitoring of peatland condition.
3. Postprocessing and modeling.
4. Stakeholder Alerts.

The fire monitoring software is a new level of service that ensures the shortest transition from information to action. The FIRMS data is crucial to alert the Ministry of Emergency Situations to fires in areas that cannot be tracked due to topography or size. Information about active FIRES is also valuable for protecting restored forest areas vulnerable to fires. Thus, the remote fire monitoring complex ensures the requirements of human safety in the modern world, contributes to the formation of a technosphere comfortable for life and human activity, minimizes technological impact on the natural environment, participates in the preservation of human life and health through the use of modern technical means, control and forecasting methods in order to protect the natural environment from negative anthropogenic impact.

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